

Management

**A STUDY ON IMPACT OF TELEVISION ADVERTISEMENT ON
CHILDREN’S ATTITUDE WITHSPECIAL REFFRENCE TO
CONFECTIONARY PRODUCT IN PALAYAMKOTTAI**

Dr. M. N. Mohamed Abusali Sheik ^{*1}, R. Mano Juliet ²

^{*1} Assistant Professor of Commerce, Sadakathullah Appa College, Tirunelveli, TamilNadu,
INDIA

² M.com, M.Phil., Research Scholar, Dept of Commerce, Sadakathullah Appa College,
Tirunelveli, TamilNadu, INDIA

ABSTRACT

In this research we investigate the impact of television advertisement on children with special reference to confectionary product in Palayamkottai. A questionnaire was used in order to collect data on impact of television advertisement on children with special reference to confectionary product different school of Palayamkottai were visited in order to collected data .The respondent agreed with this statement that there is impact of television advertisement on children with special reference to confectionary product.

Keywords:

T.V advertisement, Impact, Confectionary product.

Cite This Article: Dr. M. N. Mohamed Abusali Sheik, and R. Mano Juliet, “A STUDY ON IMPACT OF TELEVISION ADVERTISEMENT ON CHILDREN’S ATTITUDE WITHSPECIAL REFFRENCE TO CONFECTIONARY PRODUCT IN PALAYAMKOTTAI” International Journal of Research – Granthaalayah, Vol. 4, No. 4: SE (2016): 59-64.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is more popular in India. T.V Advertisement is the latest medium of mass communication and is widely used for advertisement. It is an audio-visual medium because one can see and hear .People is impressed by pictorial presentation.

CHILDREN AND T.V ADVERTISEMENT

Today’s children have a unique power in many ways from previous generation. But perhaps that most influencing on our children todays is T.V Advertisement and internet. Advertisers choose children because they are feature customers and also they are the most easily influenced and will spend their packet money if they find something interesting. Advertising to Children has long been a very successful way to build a solid consumer base that will win the mind of consumer

purchasing. Advertising to children generate jobs, injects money into the economy and instills in children at a young age the importance of freedom of choice. It also develops a child's ability to understand the value of money.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of the study is to find out the level of influence of the children's in Palayamkottai towards television advertisement and find out the factors that influence their attitude towards television advertisement and a study on the impact of television advertisement on children with special reference to confectionary product in Palayamkottai.

Sample Design

Data collection

The present study is based on both primary and secondary data required primary data were collected by using interview schedule .the respondent s selected for the studies were mostly met at their school. Secondary data collected from books, journals and websites.

Plan of analysis

After collected the necessary data from the respondent, the resescher verified the data thoroughly .the collected data was tabulated and analyzed using statistical tools like percentage, chi-square test and ANOVA.

3. ANALYSIS

Demographic characteristics of respondents

Data for the study were gathered by primary data collected throw the interview schedule method among children from Palayamkottai.

1. Majority of the respondents (54%) male children.
2. Majority of the respondent parent well educated graduate (30%) post graduate (12%) and professional course (12%).

3. Majority of the respondent fall in the age group of 12-14(71%).
4. Majority of the respondent family have two children (62%).
5. Majority of the respondent family type nuclear family (56%).

Awareness about the Television Advertisements

- The entire respondent watching T.V Regularly.
- Majority of the respondent 82% like T.V advertisement.
- Majority of the respondent 44% on an average 1hrs watching T.V
- More than the half of respondent 76% watching T.V with our parent.
- More than the half of respondent 62% says watching T.V with the purpose of take a relaxation.
- More than the half of respondent 78% feels T.V Advertisement Attract to buy the product ,most of the respondent 58% say star/models and their appearance attract more ,some of the respondent 26% say information oriented part attract more ,rest of them 14% say presentation and concept advertisement part attract more.

Features of T.V Advertisement

Regarding based on the feature of advertisement in television, the current study result revealed the type of advertisement you prefer made by children's. In ranking order respondent indicate they would mostly like to watch FUNY ADVERTISEMENT 54% ,INTERESTING and ATTRACTIVE 24%,INFOMATIVE 10%,TECHNICAL 8%,while the smallest of watch DESCRIPTIVE type of advertisement.

Factors Influence in purchasing decision

Majority of the respondent 65% says repetitive ads very influence to purchase confectionery product, 32% respondent say informative given ads less influence to purchase the confectionery product, 13% say price awareness ads very influence to purchase the confectionery product.

CHI –SQUARE TEST

HYPOTHYES

There is no significant relationship between the Age and Level of influence the T.V Ads.

AGE	T.V ADVERTISEMENT INFLUENCE LEVEL			TOTAL
	LOW	MODERTATE	HIGH	
6-8	0(0.00)	1(1.92)	7(6.08)	8
9-11	0(0.00)	6(5.04)	15(15.96)	21
12-14	0(0.00)	17(17.04)	54(53.96)	71
TOTAL	0	24	76	100

X^2 Value =0.8208 table value (at5%) =9.488 D.F= 4

Table 1 reveals that the majority of the respondent falls under the age between 12-14 years. The calculated X^2 Value =0.8208 the hypothesis less than the table value (9.488)at 5% level. Hence the hypothesis that there is no significant association between the age of the respondents and level of influence of T.V ads is accepted.

Hypothesis

There is no significant associate between the T.V viewing hours and level of influence of T.V ads.

T.V Watching Hour	Level of influence of T.V ads			Total
	low	Moderate	High	
1 hour	0.(0.00)	11(10.56)	33(33.44)	44
2 hour	0.(0.00)	5(3.60)	9(11.4)	15
3hour	0.(0.00)	4(6.96)	25(22.04)	29
Above 3 hour	0.(0.00)	3(2.88)	9(9.12)	12
Total	0.(0.00)	24	76	100

X^2 Value =3.7923 table value (at5%) =9.488 D.F= 4

Table 2 reveals that the majority of the respondents on an average 1 hour watching T.V. Calculate X^2 Value (3.7923) is less than the table value (9.488) at 5% level .hence the hypothesis that there is no significant association between the T.V viewing hours and level of influence of T.V ads is accept .

ANOVA ON TELEVISION VIEWING HOURSE BASE

		<i>SUM OF SQUARES</i>	<i>DF</i>	<i>MEAN SQUARE</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>SIG</i>
COFECTNARY PRODUCT ADVERTISEMENT	BETWEEN GRROUPS	10.115	4	2.529	6.901	.000
	WITH IN GROUPS	89.778	245	.366		
	TOTAL	99.893	249			
AGE GRROUP	BETWEEN GRROUPS	10.058	4	2.515	6.848	.000
	WITH IN GROUPS	89.971	245	.367		
	TOTAL	100.030	249			

FIND THE BEST PRODUCT ADVERTISEMENT	BETWEEN GRROUPS	3.450	4	.862	2.228	.067
	WITH IN GROUPS	94.839	245	.387		
	TOTAL	98.289	249			
ROCK MUSIC	BETWEEN GRROUPS	1.698	4	.425	.286	.887
	WITH IN GROUPS	363.085	245	1.482		
	TOTAL	364.783	249			
T.V ADVERTISEMENT	BETWEEN GRROUPS	7.950	4	1.988	3.636	.007
	WITH IN GROUPS	133.930	245	.547		
	TOTAL	141.880	249			

Confectionery product advertisement

In the above table value of the significant is .000 which is significant and tells that it is significant and alternative hypothesis is accepted and null hypothesis is rejected. It describes that age has impact on this variable.

Age group

In above table the value of the significant is .000 which is significant and tells that it is significant and alternative hypothesis is accepted and null hypothesis is rejected. It describe that the age has impact on this variable.

Find the best product advertisement

In above table the significant value is .067 which is insignificant and tells us null hypothesis is accepted and alternative is rejected.it means that age has no effect on this variable.

Rock music

In the above table the significant value is .887 which is insignificant and tells us that null hypothesis is accepted and alternative is rejected. It means that age has no this variable.

T.V Advertisement

In above table the value of the significant is .007 which is significant and tells that it is significant and alternative hypothesis is rejected.it describes that age has impact on this variable.

4. CONCLUSION

The results are positive. Yes T.V advertisement creates impact on children buying behavior and creates influence of T.V advertisement it is identified with the help of ANOVA and Chi-square test.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] Aderson, R., (1995), "*Consumer Culture and TV programming*", USA: West view Press.
- [2] Anderson, R., Engledow, J., Becker, H. (1978), "*Advertising attitudes in West Germany and the US.. an analysis over age and time*", *Journal of International Business Studies*, Vol. 9 No.3, pp.27-38.
- [3] Bever, T. G., Smith, M. L., Bengen, B., & Johnson, T. G. (1975), "*Young viewers' troubling responses to TV ads.*" *Harvard Business Review*, Vol. 53, pp 119-121.
- [4] Chauhan, R.M. (1995) "*Advertising.. The Ad challenge*", Anmol Publication, New Delhi.
- [5] Depali (1998), "*Children as Consumers*", *Indian Management*, September, pp 78.
- [6] Dr. C. Eugene Franco, and Bulomine Regi. S, "*ADVANTAGES AND CHALLENGES OF E-COMMERCE CUSTOMERS AND BUSINESSES: IN INDIAN PERSPECTIVE*" *International Journal of Research – Granthaalayah*, Vol. 4, No. 3: SE (2016): 7-13.
- [7] Golden, S. A. R., & Regi, S. B. *Mobile Commerce in Modern Business Era.*